

Functional and Radiological Evaluation of Use of Locking Compression Plating (LCP) in Treatment of Forearm Fractures in AdultsParitosh Pathak¹, Chetan Peshin², Sanad Kumar³, Siraz Malik⁴¹Junior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences, Swami Rama Himalayan University (SRHU), Dehradun, Uttarakhand²Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences, Swami Rama Himalayan University (SRHU), Dehradun, Uttarakhand^{3,4}Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Himalayan Institute of Medical Sciences, Swami Rama Himalayan University (SRHU), Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Paritosh Pathak

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Forearm fractures are on a constant rise globally, particularly prevalent among the younger demography. Though the management of these injuries operatively is well documented, use of LCP is relatively recent. There is lack of substantial evidence regarding the efficacy of LCP in comparison to other novel implants to treat forearm fractures.**Objective:** This study aims to find out the functional and radiological outcomes after using 3.5 mm locking compression plating (LCP) in treatment of forearm fractures in adults and to assess the complications, associated with the surgical management of these fractures.**Methods:** This observational follow up study comprised 36 patients who underwent Open Reduction Internal Fixation (ORIF) for treatment of forearm fractures at a tertiary care centre in north India, between July 2022 to Aug 2023. Radiological and functional outcome were assessed and followed up 1st, 3rd, 6th and 12th month postoperatively. Final functional and radiological outcome was carried out using Quick DASH score and Anderson criteria respectively.**Results:** Total 36 patients involved in this study were followed up till a duration of 12 months. Mean age was calculated out to be 33.83 ± 10.93 years ranging from 18-58 years. In the study, the primary cause for forearm fractures was attributed to road traffic accidents (n=25, 69.44%). The mean radiological union time was 13.8 weeks ranging from 9-18 weeks with 2 cases of non-union who underwent autologous bone grafting. Among 36 cases, 34 (94.44%) had no complications but the rest 2 (5.55%) had complications (superficial Surgical Site Infections) (SSI's) which were successfully treated using antibiotic therapy.**Conclusion:** Use of LCP in forearm fractures provides good to excellent results with very limited complications.**Keywords:** Forearm plating, trauma, locking compression plate (LCP), union, functional outcome.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Throughout history, forearm fracture management has undergone diverse approaches, initially emphasizing immobilization and alignment. Conventional methods encompassed the application of casts, splints, and external fixators to stabilize fractures and facilitate recovery.

These fractures typically are a consequence of trauma from high velocity, although sometimes they can also result from minor falls. The most frequent cause of injury occurs a result of axial loading of the forearm through the hand [1]. Individuals may experience persistent pain, stiffness, and limited movement in the affected arm if not treated properly and result in malunion. These issues can significantly impede everyday activities such as

lifting objects or participating in sports. Various factors, such as restoring anatomical relationships like the interosseous space between the two bones, length of radius, bowing of the radius and ulna and rotational alignment are crucial for regaining the functional capacity of the forearm [2].

Achieving anatomical reduction through open reduction and stable internal fixation with compression plating remains the gold standard treatment. However, it is important to recognize the limitations associated with plate fixation, such as the need for a sizable incision, the possibility of disrupting blood flow due to comprehensive periosteal dissection, and the heightened risk of a fracture reoccurring following the removal of the

implant [3]. The advent of Locking Compression Plating (LCP) represented a significant breakthrough in treating forearm fractures. The locking mechanism significantly improves stability, minimizes the risk of screw loosening and enables a more dependable fixation [4]. However, a thorough evaluation of using LCP (Locking Compression Plate) for forearm fractures is essential for two main reasons: function and accuracy [5]. There are limited studies regarding the effective outcome when LCP is used to treat forearm fractures.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Present study was an observational follow up study that was conducted in the Department of Orthopedics, Swami Rama Himalayan University, Swami Ram Nagar, Dehradun over a period of 12 months. Patients undergoing ORIF with plating admitted in Himalayan Institute of Medical Science who meet

the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Informed written consent was taken from each patient. Ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional ethics committee.

Sample size: The sample size was calculated by using the formula:

$$n = \frac{n \left(\frac{z_{1-\alpha}}{2} \right)^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where $\left(\frac{z_{1-\alpha}}{2} \right) = 1.96$ at 95% C.I; $p =$ Anticipated proportion = 91.5 %; $d =$ Margin of error with absolute precision = 10 %; $n = 29 \cong 30$. A total of 36 cases were taken for the study.

AO classification: The classification of fractures was done using the AO classification (Table 1).

Table 1: AO classification of fractures

AO Subtype	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
2R2A 2U2A	13	36.11
2R2A 2U2B	3	8.33
2R2A 2U2C	1	2.77
2R2B 2U2A	0	0
2R2B 2U2B	0	0
2R2B 2U2C	0	0
2R2C 2U2B	0	0
2R2C 2U2C	2	5.55
2R2A	9	25
2R2B	3	8.33
2R2C	3	8.33
2U2A	2	5.55
Total	36	

Selection of Subjects: All cases of forearm fractures undergoing ORIF with plating coming to the OPD were included in the study which fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria comprised of all fresh forearm fractures in patients between 18-60 years of age which were displaced while the exclusion criteria comprised of all patients below 18 years of age, with upper limb weakness and with pathological forearm fractures.

Study Tools: Baseline characteristics (like Age, Sex, IPD number, etc.) of the patient being brought to Orthopedic OPD / Emergency and meeting the inclusion criteria were taken in the study. The diagnosis with the procedure to be done was noted

and a written consent was taken from the patient. Preoperative preanesthetic check-up (PAC) profile of the patient was done. All patients received prophylactic antibiotics. As soon as the patient was brought for admission, a thorough clinical examination was performed which included evaluation of the musculoskeletal system to check for any other injury.

Antero-posterior and lateral radiographic X-rays of fractured forearm were taken. Patient was posted for surgery when deemed fit for same medically. Surgery was done under tourniquet under appropriate anaesthesia (regional/general). Radial exposure was carried out surgically using the Anterior Henry or

the Thompson's approach. The ulna was then opened via the subcutaneous surface on the posteromedial aspect and the posterior surface was chosen to apply the plate. While fixing the bone, first the screws were applied in compression mode and subsequent screws were applied in locking mode with at-least 3 screws on each side of the fracture.

In all patients, 3.5 mm LCP plates were used. Both DCP & LCP are used in the treatment of forearm fractures in adults, the former being commonly used,

however the final decision to use LCP is up to the discretion of the operating surgeon. The patients were called for check-up at 1st, 3rd, 6th and 12th month for functional and radiological assessment.

The results were evaluated based on fracture union, range of motion and complications like infection, delayed union etc. The Anderson et al criteria were used to determine the union status and functional outcome grading (Table 2):

Table 2: Anderson et al criteria

Results	Union	Flexion and extension at elbow joint	Supination and pronation at forearm
Excellent	Present	<10° loss	<25% loss
Satisfactory	Present	<20° loss	<50% loss
Unsatisfactory	Present	<30° loss	>50% loss
Failure	Non-union with or without loss of motion		

Subjective assessment was carried out using the QuickDASH questionnaire (Disability of the Arm, Shoulder, and Hand) which is a 11-item shortened version of the DASH outcome graded on a score of 0-100. A tally of 0 points signifies an optimally operational upper limb, reflecting the absence of any impairment, while a count of 100 points denotes the highest level of disability. The score is calculated as $\left(\left[\frac{\text{sum of } n \text{ responses}}{n}\right] - 1\right) \times 25$ where n is equal to the number of completed responses. To calculate the score, at least 10 of the 11 items must be completed.

Data Management Statistical Analysis:

Statistical analysis was initiated using a computer program, SPSS 25.0. The data present on categorical scale was expressed in terms of frequency and corresponding percentage, whereas the qualitative data was denoted as mean and standard deviation (SD).

Results

The maximum age incidence was found in the age group of 18-30 years. Mean age was calculated out to be 33.83 ± 10.93 years ranging from 18-58 years.

The cause for forearm fractures was attributed to road traffic accidents (n=25, 69.44%), fall (n=8, 22.22%) and fall of heavy object (n=3, 8.33%).

At the final 12th month of follow up, 24 (66.66%) were excellent, 9 (25%) were satisfactory, 1 (2.77%) was unsatisfactory and the remaining 2 (5.55%) were deemed as failure and did not show signs of union. They had to undergo autologous bone grafting.

The mean union time was 13.8 (range, 9-18) weeks. There were two cases of superficial infection leading to fluid discharge which subsided following antibiotic treatment (Table 3-4).

Table 3: Union status & functional outcome according to Anderson et al criteria in patients with forearm fractures at 12-month final follow up

Anderson et al criteria	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Excellent	24	66.66
Satisfactory	9	25
Unsatisfactory	1	2.77
Failure	2	5.55
Total	36	

Table 4: Complications in patients with forearm fractures

Complications	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Tourniquet palsy	0	0
Deep SSI	0	0
Superficial SSI	2	5.55
No complications	34	94.44
Total	36	

Four weeks after surgery, the mean QuickDASH score of the cases were $40.02 \pm 12.49\%$. At 12 weeks, it significantly decreased to $27.77 \pm 11.86\%$. Finally, at last follow up, being 12 months, it decreased to $20.45 \pm 12.17\%$ which is a favourable prognostic indicator (Table 5).

Table 5: Functional Outcome according to QuickDASH questionnaire in patients with forearm fractures at 12 months

QuickDASH Score	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
0 - 25	24	66.66
26 – 50	11	30.55
51 – 75	1	2.77
76 – 100	0	0
Total	36	
Mean \pm SD	20.45 ± 12.17	

Intraoperative picture, preoperative, and post-operative x-rays have been included (Figure 1). Functional ROM clinical assessment pictures are also shown (Figure 2).

Figure 1: (a) Preoperative x-ray (b) Intraoperative x ray (c) Postoperative x ray (d) 3rd month postoperative x ray (e) 6th month postoperative x ray (f) 12th month postoperative x ray

Figure 2: Functional ROM clinical assessment pictures: (a) Extension (b) Flexion (c) Pronation (d) Supination

Discussion

Locking Compression Plates (LCPs) represent an innovative type of implant featuring a distinctive 'combi-hole' design that allow the use of both a compression screw and a locking screw simultaneously [6]. Biomechanical studies have demonstrated that LCPs offer more robust fixation than traditional DCPs. Furthermore, LCPs can be applied through a technique known as bridging plate fixation, which facilitates biological healing processes for the management of complex fractures.

The benefits associated with LCPs, including enhanced fracture healing and a decrease in the incidences of cases of delayed union and nonunion, underscore their value in orthopedic treatment [7,8]. Anderson et al., in 1975, reported a union rate of 98% for fractures concerning radius and 96% for fractures of ulna, with 86% of patients achieving excellent or satisfactory results [9]. Chapman et al. reported 92% cases with excellent or satisfactory functional outcomes, with infection rate attaining 2.3% [10].

The results of our current study align with both our previous findings and the existing literature. We hypothesize that the interfragmentary compression combined with a locking internal fixator leads to a highly stable construct, although it may not always facilitate spontaneous fracture healing or callus formation. The Locking Compression Plate (LCP) provides fixed-angle stability through the use of various standard and locking head screws.

In this study, mean age of the participants accounted to 33.83 years \pm 10.93 years ranging from 18 years to 57 years. In alternate several studies which aimed

to find out the efficacy of LCP, the mean age ranged from 30 years to 38 years [9,11,12]. Out of 36 patients 27 (75%) belonged to the male category and 9 (25%) were female. In the study of Iacobellis & Biz, male was 93% and female were 7% with a male to female ratio of 13:1 [12]. The present series showed a similar percentage of males while a greater proportion (25%) of female participants than the series of Iacobellis & Biz [6]. This may be a result of greater number of osteoporotic fractures in female in the present series. In this study, road traffic accidents accounted for the majority - 25 (69.44%) which was the leading cause of mode of injury. Henle et al, (2011), in their study revealed as motor vehicle accidents being the predominant cause of injury (n = 26, 59.1%) [4].

The present study showed majority of the cases being classified under 2R2A 2U2A (36.11%) which is comparable with the study of Mushfique et al where majority of the cases were classified as 2R2A 2U2A (38.60%) [13]. The QuickDASH score at final follow up, which came out to be 20.45 \pm 12.17, was compared with recent literature. Droll et al calculated the score to be 18.6 [14], while Goldfarb et al, in their study mentioned the score to be 12 [15]. Iacobellis et al claimed the score was 13.5 while according to Manjur et al, the score was 14.6 [6,13]. On comparison, we can infer that that our study had a slight variable outcome which could be a result of delayed physiotherapeutic rehabilitation (Figure 3).

The mean radiological union time was calculated to be 13.8 weeks ranging from 9-18 weeks. It is almost comparable with mean union time of several other published studies that is statistically illustrated in the diagram below (Figure 4) [9,10,11,16,17,18].

Figure 3: Comparison of QuickDASH score with literature at final 12th month follow up: (a) Droll et al. [14], (b) Goldfarb et al. [15], (c) Iacobellis et al. [6], (d) Manjur et al. [13]

Figure 4: Comparison of mean union time (weeks) with relevant literature

Among the 36 cases, 24 (66.66%) were excellent, 9 (25%) were satisfactory, 1 (2.77%) was unsatisfactory and the remaining 2 (5.55%) were termed as failure. The percentage of patients increased from satisfactory to excellent over the follow up period signifying better recovery. 2 patients presented with poor outcome and were included in the failure category since union did not occur and they had to undergo autologous bone grafting. These findings are comparable with that of given literature. Saikia et al, (2011), found excellent in 88% cases and good in 12% of their cases [9]. Among 36 cases, 34 (94.44%) had no complications but the rest 2 (5.55%) had complications. These two patients developed superficial SSI which subsided after appropriate antibiotics therapy.

Limitation of this study would be a smaller number of patients in sample size. Further we have not done any comparison of our results with those in standard practice of LCDCP/DCP. So, our results are not comparative.

Conclusion

To conclude, use of LCPs represents an effective treatment in terms of union rate, radiological as well as functional outcome and post-operative complications. Mean union time was consistent with that reported in literature. 2 patients presented with poor outcome and were included in the failure category since union did not occur and they had to undergo autologous bone grafting. Functional outcome scores were slightly variable to that in literature. It could likely be a consequence of delayed physiotherapy rehabilitation there were low complication rates (only 2 cases of SSI's).

References

- Schulte LM, Meals CG, Neviasser RJ: Management of adult diaphyseal both-bone forearm fractures. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg.* 2014, 22:437-46. 10.5435/JAAOS-22-07-437
- Kim SB, Heo YM, Yi JW, Lee JB, Lim BG: Shaft Fractures of Both Forearm Bones: The Outcomes of Surgical Treatment with Plating Only and Combined Plating and Intramedullary Nailing. *Clin Orthop Surg.* 2015, 7:282-90. 10.4055/cios.2015.7.3.282
- Taljanovic MS, Jones MD, Ruth JT, Benjamin JB, Sheppard JE, and Hunter TB: Fracture fixation. *Radiographics.* 2003, 23:1569-90. 10.1148/rg.236035159
- Henle P, Ortlieb K, Kuminack K, Mueller CA, Suedkamp NP: Problems of bridging plate fixation for the treatment of forearm shaft fractures with the locking compression plate. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg.* 2011, 131:85-91. 10.1007/s00402-010-1119-y
- Wagner M: General principles for the clinical use of the LCP. *Injury.* 2003, 34:31-42. 10.1016/j.injury.2003.09.023
- Iacobellis C, Biz C: Plating in diaphyseal fractures of the forearm. *Acta Biomed.* 2014, 23: 202-11.
- Bartoniček J: Early history of operative treatment of fractures. *Arch Orthop Trauma Surg.* 2010, 130:1385- 96. 10.1007/s00402-010-1082-78. Molloy T, Wang Y, Murrell GA. The roles of growth factors in tendon and ligament healing. *Sports Med.* 2003; 33:381-94.
- Dodge HS, Cady GW: Treatment of fractures of the radius and ulna with compression plates. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1972, 54:1167-76.

9. Anderson LD, Sisk D, Tooms RE, Park WI 3rd: Compression-plate fixation in acute diaphyseal fractures of the radius and ulna. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1975, 57:287-97.
10. Chapman MW, Gordon JE, Zissimos AG: Compression-plate fixation of acute fractures of the diaphyses of the radius and ulna. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1989, 71:159-69.
11. Leung F, Chow SP: Locking compression plate in the treatment of forearm fractures: a prospective study. *J Orthop Surg (Hong Kong).* 2006, 14:291-4. 10.1177/230949900601400311
12. Azboy I, Demirtas A, Uçar BY, Bulut M, Alemdar C, Ozkul E: Effectiveness of locking versus dynamic compression plates for diaphyseal forearm fractures. *Orthopedics.* 2013, 36:917-22. 10.3928/01477447-20130624-23
13. Manjur M, Jalil RA, Hossen M: Outcome of LCP in Treating Diaphyseal Fractures of Radius and Ulna in Adult Patients. *Advances in Medical, Dental and Health Sciences.* 2023, 6:1-5. 10.5530/amdhs.2023.1.4
14. Droll KP, Perna P, Potter J, Harniman E, Schemitsch EH, McKee MD: Outcomes following plate fixation of fractures of both bones of the forearm in adults. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 2007, 89:2619-24. 10.2106/JBJS.F.01065
15. Goldfarb CA, Ricci WM, Tull F, Ray D, Borrelli J Jr: Functional outcome after fracture of both bones of the forearm. *J Bone Joint Surg Br.* 2005, 87:374-9. 10.1302/0301-620x.87b3.15509
16. Bhargava VK, Kumar CS, Murthy DS (2019). : Surgical management of fracture both bones forearm with locking compression plate in adult patients. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research.* 2019, 12: 130-135. 10.22159/ajpcr.2019.v12i3.28801
17. McKee MD, Seiler JG, and Jupiter JB: The application of the limited contact dynamic compression plate in the upper extremity: an analysis of 114 consecutive cases. *Injury.* 1995, 26:661-666. 10.1016/0020-1383(95)00148-4
18. Reddy JB, Abhishek L, Kathyayini R: Comparative study of forearm fractures treated with locking compression plate limited contact dynamic compression plate. *Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences.* 2015, 4:2000+.